

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE WORD HERO

Jurayeva Shalolakhon Kusanboevna¹

French language teacher,
¹Fergana State University

Jurayeva Mohinur Najmiddin qizi²

Student 22.120 group,
²Fergana state university

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Abstract

This article discusses the origin of the word hero, its meanings, the role of heroes in artistic works, their types, their influence on people's lives, and the main role of heroes in works.

Keywords: hero, artistic image, character, story, comic, work of art, type, image

Introduction

In the center of the work of art is a person with his feelings and experiences, successes and failures, positive and negative qualities. Masters of the word show a person through an image-character.

Character (French personnage, Latin persona - person) means a literary image, a hero in a work of art. The word "hero" in Uzbek is a separate person depicted in a story, and in foreign languages "character" entered the conversation as a character in literature. The traditional definition of the hero of the novel appeared in the 19th century.

In character, it means the following: personality (name, name, socio-professional status, relationships with other characters).

If we consider how the word hero is expressed in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, then it is defined as follows:

The word character comes from the Latin persona - a person, a person depicted by the author in an artistic and artistic work.

1. A man famous for his courage, courage, courage, courage and courage.

Hero of Uzbekistan is the highest title awarded for special merits in the Republic of Uzbekistan and a person who has this title.

2. The main character of a work of art. Hero of the novel. Movie characters

3. In general, the person who caused the event or played a key role in it.

4. Hero (male name).

The characters are divided into main, secondary and episodic according to the degree of their participation in the events of the work, description and generalization. The main characters are people who actively participate in the events of a work of art from beginning to end and are the bearers of the main ideological and aesthetic intention of the writer. They are called the main character of the work. Secondary characters are active characters who do not fully participate in all events, but serve to fully reveal the writer's ideological intent.

Individuals, who participate even less in the macrostructure of the work, remain episodic characters. Episodic characters serve to convincingly highlight important character traits of the protagonist.

Depending on the attitude of the writer, the characters are portrayed as positive or negative personalities. The depiction of such opposite characters in a work of art is a reference to the

age-old problem of literature that life consists of good and evil. Through the characters life events are expressed at different levels.

A character with a deep and well-drawn generalizing power rises to the level of a type. Type is the highest peak of the characters involved in a work of art. By type, symbols with less generalizing ability are called characters or characters.

In the Larousse French Dictionary, the word character is classified as follows.

The character is: 1. An important person with a social role and influence, a politician.

As synonyms, we can divide into symbols such as power, famous, great, man, enlightened.

2. Any person who attracts attention with a characteristic that is often criticized.

3. A person who plays the role of an actor and participates in a theatrical action.

4. A typical person or animal depicted in a story, comic book, movie, etc.

5. New character designer.

6. Real or imaginary person depicted in a work of art: Characters in the painting.

We have looked at their meanings and expressions in these two languages. It should be borne in mind that although it is written almost in two ways, the pronunciation is different, but the function in the work is the same.

What defines a hero?

Character, product of speech. It is believed that a fictional or real hero performed outstanding feats in the service of society. His physical devotion drove him to surpass himself, sometimes risking his life.

What are the qualities of an ancient hero?

In a fantastic setting, an ancient hero is depicted, a man with unique characteristics such as courage, strength and fighting spirit.

In the work, the reader focuses on the main character. Now, based on this concept, we can draw some conclusions. How do you know who the main character is?

The protagonist is the one through whose eyes the reader follows the story. Often this is the narrator. In fact, his point of view is the angle of the story, the best look at the appearance of the character.

What is the name of the main character?

Hero (from Greek pragonist, hero, "one who plays the lead role" in ancient Greek theatre) refers to an actor who first played the role of the protagonist and then, more broadly, took on the lead role.

What is the role of the hero in the novel?

A pillar of the romantic plot, the main object of psychological analysis and a decisive element of the story, the hero is presented as one of the important pillars of any novel. Indeed, no novel can be imagined without a character, and in any plot situation there is at least one character.

What is a minor character in a novel?

These are your most important supporting characters, usually the people closest to your characters. Thus, secondary characters come to support the heroes, help them in their search, support them. It is they who play the role of a hero and balance their character.

Character (French personnage from Latin persona "man, person") is the main character of a work of art. Characters can be completely fictional or taken from real life (story). Characters can be human, animal, supernatural, mythical, divine, or personified abstract beings.

The process of presenting information about the characters of fiction is called characterization.

As usual, the same as the literary hero. Often a hero is understood as a hero. But here, too, there are two interpretations:

Man, expressed and described in action, not in definitions; in this case, the concept of a character is more in line with the characters and roles of the dramaturgy.

Any actor is usually the object of an action. In this interpretation, the protagonist only opposes the "pure" subject of experience acting in the lyrics, so the term character is inapplicable to the so-called thing.

A character is any actor or entity that is merely a set of characteristics (character, habits, and other unique characteristics). However, in any plot, the main character is usually called the main character (and sometimes even the antagonist) - the character around whom all events take place. Therefore, if the hero is not central to the story, calling him a hero is fundamentally wrong.

On this basis, the phrase "episodic character" was formed. However, any minor or even minor character can become the main character of his story.

Literary character, image-character - any person depicted in a literary work.

All images of characters can be divided into animated and non-animated (fantasy).

Fictional characters - when creating characters, the writer relies on his imagination, fantasy, but often uses observations of specific people, who are often called the prototypes of literary characters. In the novel, along with the characters, the artistic image is important.

A historical character-character is always depicted in a work of art from the point of view of the author, returning to a specific person, reflecting his idea of a historical person. The world of characters in a certain literary work can be expressed as a system of images in which:

- a) primary, secondary and episodic signs;
- b) hero and antagonist;
- c) artistic and historical heroes;
- d) living, conditional and fictional characters;
- e) characters of different ages, social status, education and upbringing;
- f) good and bad signs;

In the figurative system of the work, all images can be associated with each, and each with all. When talking about characters, the terms hero and antihero, hero and antagonist are often used.

The hero of a work is called the protagonist of a literary work, who is the bearer of the ideals, thoughts and feelings of the writer.

An antihero is a literary character who occupies a central place in a work of art, but cannot enjoy the sympathy of the author, the antipode of the hero, and actively opposes the hero in the work in order to achieve his goal.

The portrait plays an important role in the description of the characters.

Portrait - an image of the character's appearance (face, figure, posture, facial expressions, gestures, clothes) - one of the means of describing him, the type of description. The portrait feature includes a static portrait and a dynamic one.

A static portrait gives objective, relatively stable or unchanging signs of appearance: height, physique, skin color, eyes, hair. A dynamic portrait includes facial expressions, gestures, gait features, voice, intonations.

The description of the portrait can be extended (detailed) or fragmentary (short).

The description of a portrait often combines a description of appearance and psychological characteristics. The image of the external appearance is called the external portrait, and the psychological characteristics of the character are called the psychological portrait.

No matter what language the works of art are written in, be it Uzbek or a foreign language, they influence people's lives through characters, through positive or negative characters, a person can learn a lesson and apply it to his own life. In the process of reading a work, the characters of each work occupy a place in the life of readers.

Of course, applying it to life is a sign that he has taken a deep place in our life, taking an example from him, acting like a hero of a work. The thoughts and ideas we have while reading a book can become the basis for creating our own character in our lives. We ourselves must create and choose our own positive heroism in our lives.

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